

31st International Symposium on Lepton Photon Interactions at High Energies

The Phase-2 Upgrade of the CMS Outer Tracker

Krisztina Márton
Wigner Research Centre for Physics
On behalf of the CMS collaboration

September 14, 2023

Abstract

The Large Hadron Collider at CERN will undergo a major upgrade in the Long Shutdown 3 from 2026 to 2028. The High Luminosity LHC is expected to deliver peak instantaneous luminosities up to $7.5 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and an integrated luminosity in excess of 3000 fb^{-1} in the following ten years of operation. In order to fully exploit the delivered luminosity and to cope with the demanding operating conditions, the entire silicon tracking system of the CMS experiment will have to be replaced. The Phase-2 Outer Tracker (OT) will have an increased radiation hardness, a higher granularity, and will be able to cope with larger data rates. A key feature of the CMS tracker upgrade is the inclusion of charged particle trajectories in the hardware-based (L1) trigger system. A 40 MHz silicon-based track trigger on the size of the CMS detector has never before been built; it is a novel development with the potential to not only solidify the CMS trigger strategy but to enable searches for completely new physics signatures. To achieve this, each module consists of two closely spaced sensors that are connected to the same set of readout chips. The readout chips correlate data from both sensors for a rough transverse momentum measurement. This concept will allow the trigger rates to remain at sustainable levels without sacrificing physics potential. The design of the CMS Phase-2 Outer Tracker will be presented, along with highlights from the upgrade prototyping activities.

1 Introduction

After Long Shutdown 3 (LS3), taking place in 2026-2028, the High Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC) will start colliding particles in 2029 at 14 TeV center-of-mass energy with 25 ns bunch spacing. The expected pile-up at the upgraded collider will be 140 – 200, and the peak instantaneous luminosities will be as high as $5 - 7.5 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which will result in 3000 – 4000 fb^{-1} integrated luminosity for the ten years of planned operation.

During LS3, CMS will replace its entire tracking system for the start of the new data taking phase. The new "Phase-2" Tracker [1] will consist of two parts, the Inner Tracker (IT) and the Outer Tracker (OT), both consisting entirely of silicon detector modules. To meet the requirements imposed by the unprecedentedly high luminosities at HL-LHC, the new detector is going to have increased radiation hardness (the 1 MeV neutron equivalent fluence is expected to be $2.3 \times 10^{16} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$ in the first layer of the IT, and $10^{15} \text{ n}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$ in the innermost part of the OT), higher granularity, and reduced material budget. It also has to be compatible with higher data rates and $12.5 \mu\text{s}$ trigger latency. As a new feature, the Outer Tracker will provide tracking information to the L1 trigger, allowing the trigger rates to remain at a manageable level without throwing away valuable data.

2 CMS Phase-2 Outer Tracker layout and mechanics

The layout of the Phase-2 OT is shown in Fig.1. It is composed of a barrel section with six cylindrical layers and two end-caps with five layers of double-sided disks at the ends of the barrel. The OT will be populated by two types of " p_T modules": the strip - strip (2S) and the macro-pixel - strip (PS) modules. It can be divided into three sub-detectors: the TBPS (TB2S) formed by the three inner (outer) layers of the barrel constructed from PS (2S) modules, and the TEDD in the end-caps with PS modules at $r < 60 \text{ cm}$ and 2S modules at larger radii.

Figure 1: Layout of one quarter of the CMS Phase-2 Outer Tracker in the $r - z$ plane and sketches of the sub-detectors. The blue (red) lines represent the PS (2S) modules. In the TBPS, modules are mounted on planks oriented along the beam axis in the middle part (flat section) and on rings at higher z values (tilted section). In the TB2S, modules are mounted on ladders oriented along the beam axis. In the TEDD, modules are mounted on half-disks perpendicular to the beamline, with four half-disks forming one detector layer.

The Outer Tracker will contain 7608 2S and 5592 PS modules, mounted on lightweight carbon fiber mechanical support structure, resulting in 190 m^2 total silicon area with 213 million readout channels. The operating temperature for the module sensors will be $-35 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ provided by an evaporative CO_2 cooling system.

3 The p_T modules

The basic elements of the Outer Tracker are the p_T modules. They are stand-alone units, connected directly to the detector back-end electronics. They consist of two silicon sensors, which are separated by a few millimeters and read out by common front-end electronics (Fig.2). The p_T modules are able to provide tracking information to the first level (L1) trigger by measuring the transverse momentum of the tracks and sending out self-selected information at every bunch-crossing (40 MHz).

There are two types of p_T modules, the 2S and PS, both to be constructed with different sensor spacings. They will be largely manually assembled at CMS institutes (assembly centers) with high required precision: offset between the two sensors in the direction perpendicular to the strips of $\Delta x < 50 \mu m$, distance along the strips of $\Delta y < 100 \mu m$, and tilt angle between the strips (strips and macro-pixels) smaller than $400 \mu rad$ ($800 \mu rad$) for the 2S (PS) modules.

Figure 2: Two types of the p_T modules: 2S (left side) and PS (right side).

The 2S module consists of two silicon micro-strip sensors, each with 2 columns of 1016 strips, with a single cell size of $5 \text{ cm} \times 90 \mu m$. The PS module is made from one micro-strip sensor with 2 columns of 960 strips (with single cell size of $2.5 \text{ cm} \times 100 \mu m$), and one macro-pixel sensor with 32×960 pixels (with single cell size of $1.5 \text{ mm} \times 100 \mu m$). The chosen sensor technology is Float Zone n-in-p type silicon with $290 \mu m$ active thickness. In the past years, extensive irradiation and characterization studies were performed to ensure that the FZ290 can provide sufficient signal-to-noise ratio for the whole lifetime of the detector [2].

For both module types, two front-end hybrid (FEH) electronics are connected to the two sides of the sensors. These FEHs are 4-layer, high density flexible circuits, laminated to carbon-fiber stiffener and folded back to allow wire-bonding both to the top and bottom side. Al-N spacers are used to adjust the thickness of the hybrids to the sensor-sensor spacing. The custom ASIC readout chips are flip-chip soldered directly to the FEHs. For the PS modules, there are in addition 16 MPA chips bump-bonded to the bottom side of the macro-pixel sensor, responsible for the readout of the pixels.

The powering, control, and data-transfer is provided by service electronics. They merge the data from both FEHs and then send it out via a single optical fiber to the back-end system. The powering scheme uses DC-DC converters to keep power losses and voltage drops at acceptable level. There is one service hybrid for the 2S module, and —due to its reduced width— two separate hybrid circuits for the PS (one for powering and one for readout).

4 Module prototyping and test results

During the years of the prototyping phase, functional modules with the required accuracy have been assembled by several CMS institutes. Sub-detector mechanical structure prototypes have been also built and equipped with modules to validate the designs and construction methods.

The prototype modules have been studied at various test beam facilities (CERN, DESY, FNAL), and the full readout chain has been exercised in test setups. The track segment ("stub") finding mechanism was proven to work as expected; the ability to reject particles with $p_T < 2 \text{ GeV}$ was also demonstrated. No significant drop was seen in the performance with irradiated sensors [3]. The functionality of the custom ASICs and the hybrid electronics, and the operation of the tracker DAQ software were verified [4].

Figure 3: Top: test setup at Fermilab. The "mini-module" was installed in the middle of the FTBF silicon telescope [5]. Bottom: TB2S ladder prototype, equipped with 2S modules.

The prototyping phase of the p_T modules has been concluded recently. The production of the more than 24 000 silicon sensors and the almost 50 000 hybrid electronics needed for the Phase-2 Outer Tracker has already started, the first modules assembled from the final components are expected soon. The detector construction is planned to be completed by 2026 to allow the installation in the CMS cavern during LS3.

5 QA and QC during the production period

In the next three years, more than 13 000 modules will need to be constructed, largely manually, at different CMS institutes. To guarantee similar quality by all of the assembly centers and over the entire time of the production phase, the use of the same tooling and common construction procedures and testing methods will be required. The Outer Tracker will need to operate under extreme environmental conditions without the possibility to repair or replace any of its components, so the importance of a good Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) plan is unquestionable. A detailed description of the sensor quality control process and the results from the testing of the first 20% of the silicon wafers can be found in Ref. [6].

The quality control of the hybrid electronics will consist of several steps. At the manufacturer, the circuits will be optically inspected, including taking X-ray pictures of the ASICs. Then the hybrids will go through passive thermal cycling (from $-35 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $+50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), followed by functional tests at $-35 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $+40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The electronics passing all the acceptance criteria will be sent to CMS and re-tested: all of the received hybrids will be visually inspected by CERN and

Wigner RCP (Hungary), a subset will be functionally tested at CERN, INFN Catania and INFN Genova (Italy), and long-term reliability tests will be performed at CERN and Aachen on sample basis [7].

Figure 4: Visual inspection of a front-end hybrid electronics at the Wigner RCP performed with a stereo-microscope. The cleanliness and good quality of the bond pads are crucial in the module assembly.

For all of the components, the results of each tests and measurements will be stored in a common CMS database, which will be accessible by the assembly centers during the module construction.

Acknowledgement

This work is supported by NKFIH OTKA K143477.

References

- [1] CMS Collaboration. The Phase-2 Upgrade of the CMS Tracker. *Technical Design Report*, CERN-LHCC-2017-009, CMS-TDR-014, 2017.
- [2] The Tracker group of the CMS collaboration. Selection of the silicon sensor thickness for the Phase-2 upgrade of the CMS Outer Tracker. *JINST*, 16(11):P11028, 2021.
- [3] W. Adam et al. Beam test performance of prototype silicon detectors for the Outer Tracker for the Phase-2 Upgrade of CMS. *JINST*, 15(03):P03014, 2020.
- [4] The Tracker Group of the CMS collaboration. Beam test performance of a prototype module with Short Strip ASICs for the CMS HL-LHC tracker upgrade. *JINST*, 17(06):P06039, 2022.
- [5] W. Adam et al. Test beam performance of a CBC3-based mini-module for the Phase-2 CMS Outer Tracker before and after neutron irradiation. *JINST*, 18(04):P04001, 2023.
- [6] Konstantinos Damanakis. Silicon sensors for the Phase-2 upgrade of the CMS Outer Tracker; status and early results from the production phase. *NIM A*, 1040:167034, 2022.
- [7] I. Mateos Domínguez et al. Software tools for hybrid quality control for the CMS Outer Tracker Phase-2 Upgrade. *Journal of Instrumentation*, 18(01):C01048, 2023.